

Practice Oriented Science: UAE – RUSSIA – INDIA

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HIGH-TECH PRODUCTION COMPLEXES: MODEL OF INNOVATION COMPETITION

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Abstract. *Knowledge-intensive industrial complexes in modern conditions ensure sustainable growth and competitive advantages of the world's leading national economies. The article develops an economic and mathematical model of competition for knowledge-intensive production complexes. It allows you to take into account a wide range of factors and costs that influence the efficiency and demand for created innovative products and technologies at all stages of the innovation process. Using the proposed model tools, it is possible to calculate a number of indicators of the profitability of innovative developments and the growth of social welfare. The use of model tools is aimed at analyzing the effectiveness of innovations carried out as a result of the activities of knowledge-intensive production complexes.*

Keywords: *knowledge-intensive production complex, economic development, competition, innovation, profitability, modeling.*

Introduction.

In the ranking of the world's largest economies from World Economics in terms of GDP calculated taking into account PPP, Russia was in fifth place with an indicator in dollar equivalent of not \$2 trillion, but as much as \$5.5 trillion. In the same ranking, the world's largest economy was not the United States, but China, with a PPP GDP of \$31.56 trillion. The USA comes only second with an indicator equal to \$23.15 (that is, 14% lower than the absolute size of GDP). And India took third place with a GDP at PPP of \$15.87 trillion. Japan took fourth place in the ranking with a GDP PPP of \$5.7 trillion, which is slightly higher than Russia [1].

For the Russian economy, 2023 became a year of tough sanctions. But an increase in the volume of state defense orders and the implementation of import

substitution strategies ensured the growth of Russian GDP by 3.6%. In addition, a significant contribution to the increase in this indicator was also made by the growth in construction volumes, retail sales, and the service sector. This rise in various industries was a consequence of the increase in the purchasing power of the population [2]. Meanwhile, the world economy in 2023 grew, according to the IMF, by only 2.6%, and the economy of the 19 eurozone countries by only 0.5%. At the same time, Germany, being the largest economy in the EU, generally faced a decline in GDP of 0.3%. In Germany, the economic downturn was caused by a combination of different factors, but the main ones were the country's refusal of cheap Russian pipeline gas and high interest rates in the eurozone, which negatively affected economic growth. Therefore, Germany in the GDP ranking by PPP for the second year in a row gives way to Russia as the fifth economy in the world [1].

World and domestic experience of economic development indicates that in the competitive struggle of large corporations there is competition not only for the possession of capital resources and material assets, but also for leadership in the development and implementation of innovations [3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8]. The Russian Federation, through its strategic documents (Strategy of Scientific and Technological Development [9], national projects, state programs) and speeches of political leaders, emphasizes the transition to an innovative path of development. The economic growth of knowledge-intensive industries is increasingly determined by the share of output and profit that is obtained through innovation [10, 11, 12, 13].

Purpose of the study.

To identify the features, main trends and rates of development of knowledge-intensive production complexes (R&D), analyze scientific, technical and socio-economic progress, study and introduce innovations in the context of transformation of the domestic economy, it seems appropriate to develop a model of competition in the field of scientific research and development (R&D).

Literature review.

In various works, the knowledge-intensive production complex is considered as a strategic factor or driver of sustainable economic growth [14]. In this case, private growth parameters can be divided into two groups. The first group reflects the quality of growth, and the second - the sustainability of growth dynamics.

The influence of the high-tech sector on the parameters of the quality of growth is considered in [15], which emphasizes the contribution of this sector to such a significant parameter of the quality of growth as an increase in added value. A number of works note that the possession of high-tech products and the ability to create and commercialize high technologies gives countries competitive advantages in achieving such indicators of the quality of growth as conquering new markets and increasing the export of non-resource, non-energy goods [16, 17]. Work [16] highlights the contribution of the high-tech sector to indicators of the quality of

growth, reflecting the return on production resources: labor productivity, material and energy intensity of production.

The impact of the high-tech sector on parameters related to the sustainability or stability of growth dynamics has been highlighted in a number of studies. Some of them emphasize the contribution of the high-tech sector to the country's innovative potential [18]. It can be rightfully interpreted as a significant resource for sustainable growth and development. Investment is essential to maintaining growth rates. In [19], using the example of a number of Russian high-tech companies, it is shown that the investment attractiveness of these companies shows an increasing trend. Based on the Economic Complexity Index (ECI), the author of the article [20] shows that countries exporting products of high technological complexity are more likely to demonstrate sustainable growth dynamics. The competitive advantages of these countries are determined by the complexity of organizing production processes, which require possession of technical know-how and the involvement of highly qualified personnel with special skills. There is also a higher resistance of technologically complex goods to economic shocks [21], which is important for Russia against the backdrop of sanctions pressure from "unfriendly" countries.

Materials and methods.

To solve the problem, methods of a system-target approach, generalization of publicly available scientific and information materials, statistical and structural analysis, and logical interpretation of economic phenomena are used.

Research results.

To do this, let us assume that perfect competition is realized in the production sector, which means that all R&D companies (firms, enterprises, corporations and their associations), whose interests are financially coordinated, initially have the opportunity to use the same modern technology and, per one product, produce knowledge-intensive products with constant marginal costs c . Let us also assume that in the field of R&D there is an oligopolistic equilibrium, which is characterized by constant costs for the development of progressive high-tech products for various purposes. Under these conditions, it would be fair to assume that: all R&D subjects compete with each other to create an innovation (state registration and obtaining a patent), which is then licensed; the introduction of innovation will entail a reduction in R&D production costs to the level $(c-d)$, where d – the patent owner's revenue for each product manufactured.

Let us introduce the following notation:

H – income of the owner of an innovative patent received over the entire period of its validity;

J – growth of social welfare (if it occurs) due to the use of innovation over the entire period of validity of the patent (it cannot be appropriated by the owner of the patent, but can be used by consumers and other production associations);

K – deadweight loss that occurs during the patent’s lifespan, since potential increases in social welfare can only begin after the patent’s lifespan, and welfare does not increase during the patent’s lifespan due to the monopolistic ownership of additional income by the patent holder).

Let’s pretend that H , J and K are stationary flows. Then the value H is always positive, and the quantities J and K greater than or equal 0 ($J \geq 0$ и $K \geq 0$).

To characterize demand, we introduce the function $Q(P)$. We will consider innovation radical in the case where the monopoly price is determined by new (reduced) marginal costs ($c-d$), becomes lower than the corresponding previous marginal cost c . Imitation of innovation (patented technology) can be considered as the creation of R&D of one’s own technology, created on the basis of information data about the final product that was produced using the patented technology, and, as a rule, inferior in quality to the patented one [6, 7]. In the case where the innovation cannot be considered radical and cannot be imitated, the patent holder must license the new innovative technology with a payment per unit of the product equal to d . In this situation, in order to achieve post-innovation equilibrium, product output will remain at the initial (pre-innovation) level $Q_0 = Q(c)$, and the income of the patent owner is determined by the product of the cost of pre-innovation output and the reduction in production costs d . In Fig.1 this income is presented graphically as the area of a rectangle H .

Figure 1. Non-radical innovation.

Free access to advanced technology opens when the patent expires and the level of output increases to $Q_1 = Q(c-d)$, and the price is determined by the value of the new significantly reduced marginal costs [8]. In this case, the deadweight

loss, which is due to patent licensing, graphically corresponds to the area of the triangle K (see fig.1).

In the case of radical innovation, the patent holder issues licenses to use the new innovative technology to interested R&D companies, charging a fee graphically corresponding to the area of the rectangle H (see fig.2). In this case, the main difference from the previously considered case is that some part of the increase in social welfare received by society before the end of the patent’s validity period is not appropriated by the patent owner [9]. In Fig. 2 this part graphically corresponds to the area of the figure J .

Figure 2. Radical innovation.

A similar situation arises when a patent has a very long period of time, and R&D is not able to imitate a new innovative technological process. The level of costs of R&D subjects will remain at the pre-innovation level, equal to c . But if the time limits of the patent turn out to be narrow, then R&D subjects can imitate the innovation without violating the licensing terms of the patent, and to some extent reduce their costs. A measure of the time period of a patent is the share of reduction in production costs that is not transferred to R&D as a freely available technology. Therefore, defining the scope of a patent through γ , it is possible to formalize the marginal costs of R&D that imitate a new innovative technology as follows – $(c-\gamma d)$. As a result we get $J>0$, which will reflect the difference between private and public benefits from the created and applied innovation throughout the entire period of validity of the patent.

From moment T , which corresponds to the end of the patent's validity period, the equilibrium price falls to the value $(c-d)$, and social welfare will increase by K .

Using the introduced notations and taking into account the above reasoning, we can proceed directly to developing a model of competition between R&D subjects that arises at the initial stages of the innovation process. In the field of R&D, when creating a patentable innovation, competition occurs between several R&D entities. At a moment in time $t=0$ each competing participant determines the scope of R&D x_i and incur one-time research costs αx_i , where α – marginal (allowable) costs for implementing the R&D program. The volume of R&D allows you to calculate the time period required for the successful completion of all planned research and development work. Assuming that the timing of the innovation i -blm by the R&D subject is distributed exponentially and does not depend on the time of development of the innovation by other R&D subjects, the probability of successful completion of the entire set of works i -blm by the R&D subject at the time t or earlier is $(1-a^{-x_i t})$. Win function s_i , subject i ($i=1, \dots, n$) represents the amount of expected income without the costs of complex R&D, that is:

$$s_i = \int_0^{\infty} \exp[-(\sum_{j=1}^n x_j + r)t] x_i V dt - \alpha x_i - F = \frac{x_i V}{\sum_{j=1}^n x_j + r} - \alpha x_i - F, \quad (1)$$

where r – percent rate;

V – real value of income received i -blm R&D subject;

αx_i – variable costs associated with R&D;

F – fixed costs associated with R&D.

In the moment $t=0$ both variable and fixed costs are paid.

Value $\exp[-(\sum_{j=1}^n x_j)t]$ there is a probability of a process in which by the time t none of the R&D subjects was able to develop the planned innovation.

Income V the patent holder is determined by the discounted revenues from licensing the patented technology:

$$V = \int_0^T H \alpha^{-rt} dt = zH/r, \quad (2)$$

where $z = 1 - \alpha^{-rT}$ – value of discounted income H/r , received by the patent holder.

Each R&D subject chooses an R&D investment option that maximizes expected income (1). The necessary condition for a maximum can be represented by the following formula:

$$\frac{(X_{-i} + r)V}{(r + X_{-i} + x_i)^2} = \alpha, \quad (3)$$

where $X_{-i} = \sum_{j \neq i}^n x_j$.

It is easy to show that this condition is satisfied. To do this, let us assume that all subjects of the NPC are identical and study the symmetrical equilibrium characterized by the relation $x_i = x$ for all i . In this case, condition (3) takes the form:

$$\frac{[(n-1)r+r]V}{(r+r\alpha)^2} = \alpha. \tag{4}$$

In further consideration of the problem, we will assume that all R&D subjects have the opportunity to carry out R&D. Then the number of such entities in the sector under study is endogenous and the profit for them becomes zero:

$$\frac{rV}{nx+r} - \alpha x - F = 0. \tag{5}$$

Equations (4) and (5) determine the equilibrium number of RPC subjects n and x :

$$(nx+r)^2 = x^2V/F.$$

Substituting this expression into equation (5), we obtain

$$x = (\sqrt{FV} - F)/\alpha; \tag{6}$$

$$n = \sqrt{\frac{V}{F}} - \frac{r\alpha}{\sqrt{FV} - F}. \tag{7}$$

At the same time, the equilibrium number of R&D subjects in the industry becomes a decreasing function, depending on the constant costs of R&D F . At $F \rightarrow 0$ the scientific research sector is becoming completely competitive.

Integral investment in R&D $X=r\alpha$ amounts to:

$$X = \frac{1}{\alpha} \left(\frac{zH}{r} - \sqrt{\frac{zFH}{r}} \right) - r. \tag{8}$$

But even with a guarantee of maximum patent protection, the patent policy pursued by the state will become ineffective if the institutions that regulate and stimulate innovative economic activity do not make the necessary investment in R&D carried out by R&D. Therefore, it would be logical to assume that an infinite patent period increases investment and leads to a situation where $X > 0$. Designated by \bar{T} the minimum period of patent validity at which there is an equilibrium and positive investment in R&D, and $\bar{z} = 1 - \alpha^{-r\bar{T}}$, we get that:

$$\bar{z} = \frac{r}{H} \left(\frac{\sqrt{F}}{4} + \sqrt{\frac{F}{4} + \alpha r} \right)^2 \tag{9}$$

Next, suppose that $\bar{z} < 1$. This assumption requires the following inequality to hold:

$$\frac{H}{r} > \left(\frac{\sqrt{F}}{4} + \sqrt{\frac{F}{4} + \alpha r} \right)^2. \tag{10}$$

In the extreme case when $F = 0$, this inequality reduces to the following form:

$$\sqrt{\frac{H}{\alpha}} > r. \tag{11}$$

Conclusion.

As a result of the research, the authors developed a model of competition among R&D subjects. It allows you to take into account the combination of many factors and costs that influence the effectiveness of innovative products and technologies at all stages of the innovation process. It is advisable to use model tools when analyzing the effectiveness of innovations carried out by various knowledge-intensive production complexes.

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